

EFFECTS OF MODERN TECHNOLOGY ON STUDENTS' LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the effects of modern technology on the learning of students at the College of Teacher Education, Jose Rizal Memorial State University during the 1st semester of 2023-2024. Using a descriptive research method and a validated researcher-made quantitative survey, the study aimed to understand the relationship between technology use and learning outcomes. The survey was administered to a selected group of students. The results revealed that most students were females in their early 20s, from low-income families, spending an average of 6-7 hours daily on devices like mobile phones, laptops, desktops, and tablets. The study found that modern technology had both positive and negative effects. While it improved communication and task completion, it also had negative impacts on relationships, particularly between parents and children. Statistical tools, including percentage computation, weighted mean, and Chi-square tests, were used to analyze the data and examine the relationship between technology use and student profiles. Based on these findings, the study recommended that students control their screen time to mitigate negative effects, especially on relationships. Parents may engage more with their children by spending quality time and offering guidance. Additionally, instructors may incorporate alternative learning methods, such as on-site discussions and library sessions; to reduce screen time and promote better learning experiences. This study emphasizes the importance of balancing technology use with face-to-face interactions and other educational strategies for optimal student development.

Keywords: *modern technology, students' learning, effects, gadget, frequency usage*

INTRODUCTION

The integration of modern technology into education has fundamentally altered the way students engage with learning. With the widespread use of devices such as smartphones, laptops, and tablets, technology has become an integral part of students' daily lives, offering significant benefits such as increased access to information, enhanced creativity, and personalized learning opportunities (Dyhrkopp, 2021). However, the pervasive use of these devices also raises concerns about their impact on student behavior and academic performance. While technology has proven beneficial in providing students with the tools needed for remote learning, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic (Valenzuela, 2021), its overuse can lead to distractions, reducing students' focus on their studies and causing disruptions in their educational process.

The literature highlights the dual nature of technology's effects on education. On one hand, it improves learning experiences by fostering engagement, collaboration, and digital literacy (Dyhrkopp, 2021). On the other hand, excessive smartphone use is associated with psychiatric, cognitive, emotional, medical and brain changes that should be considered by health and education professionals (Wacks & Weinstein, 2021). Despite the widespread recognition of both positive and negative outcomes, there remains a gap in understanding how technology specifically affects students' conduct in the educational context.

This study is timely and relevant, particularly as education systems globally continue to rely on technology to bridge gaps in learning, especially during crises. The research will explore how the use of modern technological devices impacts student behavior and learning, with the aim of addressing potential issues such as over-reliance on gadgets and ensuring that technology is used effectively to enhance academic outcomes. The findings of this study will contribute to the growing body of literature on technology in education, offering insights into how it can be integrated responsibly to improve both learning outcomes and student conduct.

Research Questions

This study aims to investigate the effects of using modern technology on the learning of students enrolled in the College of Education during the 1st semester 2023-2024.

Specifically it attempts to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender;
 - 1.3 Annual Family Income; and
 - 1.4 Frequency Usage of Gadgets?
2. What are the types of modern technology gadgets used?
3. What are the effects of modern technology on the students' learning in terms of;

- 3.1 Communication;
- 3.2 Accomplish specific task; and
- 3.3 Relationship in terms of:
 - 3.3.1 parents; and
 - 3.3.2 peer?

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted at Jose Rizal Memorial State University – Dipolog Campus, specifically focusing on the College of Teacher Education students for the school year 2023 - 2024. The respondents were randomly selected from the students enrolled in the College of Teacher Education during this period. The study primarily aimed to identify the profile of the respondents, the types of gadgets they used, and the effects of modern technology on their learning experiences. The researchers used a researcher-made questionnaire to collect data from the respondents. Before conducting the study, the questionnaire was submitted to critics, a statistician, the adviser, and qualified professors for feedback and suggestions to ensure its comprehensiveness and the appropriateness of each item. This process helped refine the instrument to ensure its validity. The questionnaire was composed of three parts. Part I aimed to determine the profile of the respondents, including variables such as age, gender, annual family-income status, and frequency of gadget usage. Part II focused on identifying the types of modern technology gadgets used by the respondents. Finally, Part III sought to determine the effects of modern technology on the students' learning experiences, specifically focusing on how these devices influenced their academic behavior and performance. By dividing the questionnaire into these sections, the researchers were able to gather both demographic and behavioral data, which facilitated a comprehensive analysis of the impact of modern technology on students' learning.

Prior to the distribution of the questionnaire, the researchers sought approval from the Associate Dean of the College of Teacher Education at Jose Rizal Memorial State University – Dipolog Campus. Once approval was granted, the researchers proceeded with the random selection of respondents to participate in the survey. Communication with the respondents occurred during the distribution of the questionnaire, where they were instructed to answer all questions in the survey. The researchers ensured that all items were answered by checking the questionnaires for any incomplete responses. Upon retrieval, the completed questionnaires were tallied and tabulated. The tallied data were then reviewed and finalized before being forwarded for statistical treatment, which was conducted by an authorized statistician on campus.

RESULTS

Table 1 Respondent's Profile in Terms of Age

Age Bracket	f	Percentage
18 - 20 years old	26	37.14 %
21 - 23 years old	36	51.43%
24 – 26 years old	6	8.57%
27 years old and above	2	2.86%
Total	70	100 %

Table 2 Respondent's Profile in Terms of Sex

Sex	f	Percentage
Male	9	12.86%
Female	61	87.14%
Total	70	100 %

Table 3 Respondent's Profile in Terms of Monthly Family Income

Monthly Family Income	f	Percentage
below P10,957	36	51.43%
Php10,957 to Php21,914	34	48.57%
Total	70	100 %

Table 4 Respondent's Profile in Terms of Frequency Usage of Gadgets

Frequency Usage of Gadgets	f	Percentage
1-3 hours	18	25.71%
4-5 hours	20	28.57%
6-7 hours	21	30.00%
8hours and above	11	15.71%
Total	70	100 %

Table 5 Types of Modern Technology Gadgets Used by the Respondents

Modern Technology Used	f	Percentage
Android Phone	66	94%
Laptop	41	59%
Tablet	9	13%
Computer Desktop	31	44%

Table 6 Effects of Modern Technology on the Students' Learning in terms of Communication

Statements	WM	Description
1. Makes communication easier, quicker and more efficient between co-students and instructors through the use of emails, live chats, and video conference.	4.54	Strongly Agree
2. Helps tracks previous conversation to remember what was the topic all about through back-reading the chat box.	4.46	Strongly Agree
3. Increases communication with co-students and educators through emails, online agendas, discussion boards and the likes.	4.38	Strongly Agree
4. Able to participate with the discussion despite the distance between co-students and educators through video conference/call.	4.21	Strongly Agree
5. Gathers a wide audience when posting concerns, ideas, and other write-ups regarding the school, and/or the course subjects on social media sites.	4.37	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.39	Strongly Agree

Table 7 Effects of Modern Technology on the Students' Learning in terms of Accomplish Specific Task

ACCOMPLISH SPECIFIC TASK	WM	Description
1. Can complete the activities before the scheduled due date.	4.06	Agree
2. Easier access on other resources as guide in doing specific task.	4.31	Strongly Agree
3. Critically reflects on contents to fully understand the subject matter.	4.11	Agree
4. Promotes convenience when doing specific tasks especially doing research about the subject matter.	4.45	Strongly Agree
5. Boosts students' interests in finishing specific task as it allows them to surf the internet for more interesting insight about the subject matter.	4.25	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.24	Strongly Agree

Table 8 Effects of Modern Technology on the Students' Learning in terms of Relationship

RELATIONSHIP	WM	Description
A. Parents		
1. Declines parent-children relationship because students' excessive attention put on technology used.	3.79	Agree
2. Develops difficulty for parents to engage in an open and honest communication with their children.	3.85	Agree
3. Limits family interaction since both parents and children are more focused on what is happening online that what is happening within the family.	3.96	Agree
4. Increases conflict between parent and children.	3.86	Agree
5. Helps communicates to children studying away from home.	4.28	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	3.95	Agree
B. Peers		
1. Collaborates more with other co-students during interactive discussions through live chats.	4.38	Strongly Agree
2. Promotes peer-to-peer interaction despite the distance between them through video conference.	4.25	Strongly Agree
3. Reaches out to co-students more quickly regarding home works through e-mail, chats, or texts using cellphones.	4.25	Strongly Agree
4. Understands other's thoughts through their shared posts on social media.	4.06	Agree
5. Facilitates exchange of views in academic as well as personal matters among co-students and educators.	4.13	Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.21	Strongly Agree
General Weighted Mean	4.08	Agree

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the respondents' profile in terms of age. It can be observed in the table that most of the respondents are from ages 21-23 years old. Hence, over half of the respondents are in their early twenties.

Table 2 presents the respondents' profile in terms of sex. It can be observed that most of the respondents are females. Hence, female students outnumbered male students at the College of Teacher Education. This implies that there is sex imbalance in the college. However, it can also be infer that college is an inclusive department in terms of sex. This is highly supported by Capahay (2021) statement saying that there is only one occupation where males noticeably form the group of minority. She highlighted that the teaching courses were mainly dominated by females. This is also supported by Regalado (2017) emphasizing that more females are enrolled in education courses.

Table 3 presents the respondents' profile in terms of monthly family income. It can be observed in the table that majority of the respondents belonged from lower income families. This implies that students belonged from the poor class based on the country's income classification. This further infers that the university is intended for students that belong to families with less income that seeks quality tertiary education. Chua (2021) highlighted the income classification of families living in the Philippines based on the classification released by the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS) in the year 2021. According to the article, families that earn between Php10,957 to Php21,914 monthly income belong to lower income but not poor, and below P10,957 monthly income in considered poor. In connection to this, Daway-Ducanes et al. (2022) pointed that state universities in the country are advised to promote an alternative and equitable admission that enhances the access of disadvantage students such as indigenous students, poor and deserving students.

Table 4 presents the respondents' profile in terms of frequency usage of gadgets. It can be observed in the table that there 2nd and 3rd year students usually use gadgets for 6-7 hours daily. This implies that respondents use gadgets with in the average screen time of the people around the world (Howarth, 2023).

Howarth (2023) highlighted that the average person spends 6 hours and 58 minutes per day on screens connected to the internet and is likely to continue to grow (Howarth, 2023). Moreover, Narsico and Flores (2023) highlighted that in the Philippines, adolescents who used screens for more than seven hours per day had a forty percent reduced chance of academic success, whereas those who used screens for two to four hours per day had a one-and-a-half times greater chance of earning excellent grades.

Table 5 presents the respondents' profile in terms of types of modern technology gadgets used by the respondents. It can be observed in the table that among the respondents, android phone was commonly used followed by laptop and computer desktop, while few only use tablets. This further implies that students use variety of gadgets to aid their day to day studies. Android phone is the most commonly used gadget as it is one of the most affordable gadget a student could get. Laptop and computer desktop are also used by the students as they are more convenient to use than mobile phone as it offer wide screen with connected keyboards for faster typing. Tablets, on the other hand, are handy yet expensive than mobile phones.

This is highly supported by the findings of Statista Research Department (2023) that as of the third quarter of 2022, ninety-seven point three percent of internet users in the Philippines accessed the web via mobile devices, such as feature phones and smartphones. Conversely, sixty-four point eight percent of respondents indicated that they accessed the internet via a desktop or laptop, which may have been their personal computer or one provided by their employer.

Similarly, in the study of Cleofas and Rocha (2021), it was found out that majority of the students own a smartphone and own only one type of gadget. Additionally, in terms

of Internet connectivity, the majority of the participants have their own subscription to a cellular or mobile service and have unlimited access.

Table 6 presents the effects of modern technology on the students' learning in terms of communication. The result implicates that modern technology has positive effects when it comes to communications. It provides efficient communication between students and instructors, between co-students, and between co-instructors. Moreover, it helps increased connectivity among students as it brings divers students to one aiming to get informed and learn from the discussions.

According to Schindler et al. (2017), students are emotionally and cognitively engaged by technology in the following ways: through increased effort and time spent on learning activities; through improved attitudes and interests toward learning; and through cognitive investment in comprehending content. Increased opportunities for student engagement, collaboration with peers, and instructor-mentor interaction are afforded through the integration of technology, whether it is during school hours or outside of it. Technological advancements such as digital games, blogs, wikis, web-conferencing software, and social networking sites have been demonstrated to increase student engagement.

Moreover, D'Angelo (2018) highlighted that in light of the escalating integration of technology into the labor market and educational institutions, it is critical that pupils acquire a comprehensive understanding of a multitude of digital applications. By incorporating technology into the curriculum, educational institutions not only afford students the chance to enhance their skill sets and achieve academic success, but they also equip them with the necessary preparations to navigate the challenges they will face after they graduate. Although educational technology facilitates a shift in focus from the instructor to the learners, it is critical that instructors conscientiously consider viable approaches for its successful integration.

Table 7 presents the effects of modern technology on the students' learning in terms of accomplish specific task. The result implicates that modern technology has positive effects when it comes to accomplishing specific task. Elaborately, Modern technology has revolutionized research and academic tasks by providing rapid information accessibility, efficient data gathering, collaboration, advanced search capabilities, easy access to learning materials, organization and citation tools, and adaptive learning platforms. These advancements enhance the research process, improve collaboration, and enhance the educational experience, making it more accessible, efficient, and effective.

Leonard (2019) highlighted that the efficiency, productivity, information accessibility, customization, collaboration, time management, creativity, adaptive learning, and global learning opportunities of students have been substantially enhanced by modern technology. It facilitates streamlined processes, grants users access to a wide range of resources, and enables individualized learning experiences. Digital tools such as messaging platforms and video conferencing facilitate communication and

collaboration, whereas calendar applications and task managers aid in meeting deadlines.

Additionally, Lees (2020) emphasized that students are empowered to articulate their thoughts in novel and inventive fashions through the use of creative software tools, while adaptive learning functionalities evaluate student advancement and modify course material accordingly. Global learning opportunities enable students to access resources, guest lectures, and specialists from around the globe, thereby overcoming geographical barriers. In general, contemporary technology enables learners to be more effective in academic and non-academic spheres through the provision of tools, platforms, and resources that improve collaboration, learning experience, and overall task completion.

Table 8 presents the effects of modern technology on the students' learning in terms of relationship towards parents and peer. The result implicates that modern technology has both negative and positive impact to parent-children relationship. It greatly helps one another communicates while children are studying away from home. However, it reduces family interaction because both parents and children are preoccupied with online activities rather than family matters.

Walkers (2019) suggest that parental distraction by technology can compromise secure attachment and, consequently, child development. Moreover, Mackay et al. (2022) highlighted that overuse of technology may harm the bond between parents and children by lowering communication, decreasing quality time spent together, setting a bad example for conduct, and having a negative behavioral influence. This may result in a decrease in in-person interactions, a weakened comprehension of in-person connections, and trouble developing stable bonds. Furthermore, too much screen time might impede bonding activities and result in relationships that are less cohesive. Children who rely too much on technology run the risk of isolating themselves and losing their feeling of family unity. Rules regarding screen time might sometimes give rise to disputes. Technology usage, age, and family dynamics may all affect how technology affects parent-child interactions. To lessen these difficulties and promote a better parent-child bond, families should balance technology usage and set up appropriate limits.

In term of peer relationship, it implies that the use of modern technology offers positive outcome among the students. It helps them communicate with one another in the most convenient and efficient way during discussions and virtual interactions.

According to Courtney and Nowakowski-Sims (2018), digital technology and social networking sites have the potential to facilitate healthful socialization and enhance the well-being of both adolescents and adults. This connection may be of the utmost importance for parents in order to preserve their social support networks. Social support systems reduce depressive and anxious symptoms and facilitate parent-on-parent discussions of parenting techniques. Moreover, social connectedness is crucial for emotional health and can aid in the reduction of anxiety and depression as well as enhance a person's overall life satisfaction. Social connectedness may facilitate the introduction of parents to additional support systems, thereby enhancing their parenting

abilities. Individuals who are deprived of significant relationships may find solace in the regular social interaction facilitated by social media. This sense of belonging can provide support to new mothers who are otherwise isolated.

Additionally, McLean (2021) highlighted that with the use of gadgets such as mobile phones and laptops, student learning is enhanced as they integrate these social interactions into their learning environment, which facilitates the overlap of skills. Scholars are in agreement that student collaboration improves self-control, problem-solving, and additional executive functioning abilities.

Conclusions

This study concludes that most of the students are females in their early 20s. They belonged from poor to lower income families. They spend an average 6-7 hours on their gadgets such as mobile phones, laptop, computer desktop and tablet. It was found out that there when it comes to communication and accomplish specific task, positive impacts are noted. However, in terms of relationship, there were both positive and negative effects on the use of modern technology among students.

Recommendations

Based on the summary of findings and the conclusions derived, the following recommendations were offered:

1. Students may control their screen time in using modern technology to avoid its negative effects especially when it comes to parent-children relationship. However, make use of the gadget efficiently in studies to improve their skills.
2. Parents/Guardian are advise to spend with their children through bonding, talking, guiding, and interacting with them to strengthen parent-children relationship without jeopardizing their studies.
3. Parents may limit the screen time of their children by giving them extra house chores or practice regular family outdoor recreational activities that may help them refrain from using modern technology if unnecessary.
4. Instructors may provide alternative learning delivery that may help reduce screen time activities of students such as giving on-site discussion, library session, and providing materials that will serve as their resources for the day to day lessons.
5. Future researchers may further utilize and conduct similar study by using other possible variables that may have an impact with students' learning in the new generation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Research ethics governed the standards of conduct for the researchers, ensuring the protection of participants' dignity, rights, and welfare. It was crucial to adhere to these

ethical principles throughout the research process. To maintain ethical integrity, the researchers ensured that all pre-formalities, including the approval and signing of necessary letters, were completed before beginning the study. The researchers respected the rights of participants, acknowledging their autonomy to decide whether to volunteer for the study or not. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring that they fully understood the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks. The consent form was signed by the researchers' adviser, a school official, and the lead teacher to minimize harm and maximize benefits for all involved. These ethical actions guided the researchers in conducting the study with respect and responsibility, prioritizing the well-being of the participants.

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